

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

METHOD FOR DETERMINING THE FLUID TENSION COEFFICIENT USING THE LOGARITHMIC APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This article is about studying the leakage of volumes from physical objects like voluminous bodies carrying necessary liquid products. The idea is to investigate the wetting coefficient of a liquid flowing through an assumed circular opening, so that one can investigate the situation by changing the material of the opening, and the physical nature of the substance that can flow through the opening. The work is proposed as an improvement and the development of the methodology for studying the coefficient of fluid tension in laboratory work conducted by the University of Life Safety, concerned with the fluid tension coefficient and fire safety of the endangered objects. The fluid tension coefficient is modelled, and the accuracy of the calculation is assessed using a logarithmic approach.

Keywords: study, fluid tension, logarithmic approach.

Fundamentals of the Investigation. The research in this paper is devoted to the determination of surface tension using capillary tubes under the influence of the inclination of these tubes and the size of the holes, which are associated with the flow of liquids, the surface tension coefficient of which is determined. Previous studies (see [1, 2]) do not take into account the possibility of determining the tension coefficient using a single tube, as well as the inclination of the tubes when fluid flows through them. However, in practice, there are often cases where circular holes or those close to them are of different diameters and are inclined differently, which requires additional insight into the situation with the influence of the tension coefficient of the flowing liquids. This work is devoted to considering such a situation, when various materials holes can be used in objects that are equivalent to the capillaries, with similar coefficient of fluid tension for the fire service safety.

Model of experiment. The study of internal molecular pressure in capillaries and small holes in a liquid due to surface tension is described by Laplace's formula [3]. According to Laplace the pressure difference Δp on both sides of the capillary surface with two mutually perpendicular radii of circles corresponding to two circles R_1 i R_2 appears in the form

$$\Delta p = \sigma \left(\frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{R_2} \right),$$

with the coefficient of surface tension σ .

For the purpose of practical evaluation of the coefficient of fluid tension and typical openings which are in practice we can assume that the radius of the capillary opening is close to circular then the radii of the mutually perpendicular R_1 and R_2 can be equal (or can be considered) equal. In this case, the changes in the liquid pressure in the vertical direction along the meniscus with radius R can be represented taking into account the tension in the form $\Delta p = \frac{2\sigma}{R}$. If we assume that the force of gravity of the liquid restrained by tension on the meniscus can be represented in the form $\Delta p =$

ρgh , where, respectively, ρ is the density, g the acceleration of gravity h is the height of the restrained fluid due to the tension coefficient, then we can calculate the tension coefficient by the formula

$$\sigma = 0.5R\rho gh. \quad (1)$$

In the latter formula, if we take the density ρ of the liquid wetting the capillary and the acceleration of gravity g as known quantities, it is necessary to measure the height h of the column of liquid wetting the capillary and take into account the radius of the drop that can be thrown or dropped by the capillary of the liquid wetting it. We take the shape of a spherical drop with a radius R which is equal to half the diameter d of the capillary.

The volume of one drop is calculated using the formula

$$V = \frac{\pi d^3}{6}. \quad (2)$$

In this case, the volume of the liquid column h in the capillary is equal to the volume of N drops:

$$N \frac{\pi d^3}{6} = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} h.$$

From the last equality we can find the height of the liquid column in the capillary h , use formula (1) to determine the coefficient of fluid tension and formula (2) to determine the volume of the drop and we will obtain the value of the determination of the fluid surface tension coefficient (1) in the form

$$\sigma = \frac{\rho V g}{\pi d N}, \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the acceleration of gravity, ρ is the density of the liquid under study, V – the volume of liquid in the wetted capillary, d is the diameter of the capillary, and N is the number of drops in the volume of the capillary of the liquid under study in the experiment.

Surface tension coefficient and errors. To find relative error of the surface tension coefficient of the liquid under study, we will use the logarithmic method. For this we logarithmize the fluid tension coefficient (3) [4]:

$$\ln \sigma = \ln \rho + \ln V + \ln g - \ln \pi - \ln d - \ln N.$$

Differentiating the resulting expression we will have

$$\frac{D\sigma}{\sigma} = \frac{D\rho}{\rho} + \frac{DV}{V} + \frac{Dg}{g} - \frac{D\pi}{\pi} - \frac{Dd}{d} - \frac{DN}{N}.$$

Taking into account that errors can only accumulate and grow, in the last expression we change the minus sign to a plus sign. We will have

$$\frac{D\sigma}{\sigma} \leq \frac{D\rho}{\rho} + \frac{DV}{V} + \frac{Dg}{g} + \frac{D\pi}{\pi} + \frac{Dd}{d} + \frac{DN}{N}.$$

Differentials from constant quantities such as the acceleration of gravity g and the number π are equal to zero, therefore, replacing all differentials with experimental errors, we will have

$$\varepsilon = \frac{D\sigma}{\sigma} \leq \frac{D\rho}{\rho} + \frac{DV}{V} + \frac{Dd}{d} + \frac{DN}{N}. \quad (4)$$

The obtained expression makes it possible to find the absolute error of the experiment

$$\Delta\sigma = \varepsilon\sigma.$$

Calculations. We studied the surface tension coefficient for tap water. The experimental data are as follows: capillary diameter $d = 0.445 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m, number of drops $N = 212$, density of water $\rho = 1000$ kg/m³, volume of water $V = 2 \cdot 10^6$ m³, acceleration due to gravity $g = 9.81$ m/sec². Surface tension coefficient according formula (3) for the tap water obtained

$$\sigma = \frac{\rho V g}{\pi d N} = 0.066 N/m. \quad (5)$$

The error of the experiment would be around 10% according to formula (4), where all differentials were determined with an accuracy of 1/10%.

The surface tension coefficient for water at 20°C has a value by authors Halliday & Resnick of the book *Fundamentals of physics* [5] $\sigma = 0.0728 N/m$. Tap water containing impurities partially weakens molecular interaction and tension, in particular the coefficient of surface tension, and it decreases. Tap water containing impurities partially weakens molecular interaction and tension, in particular the coefficient of surface tension, and it decreases. Therefore, the result obtained as a result of experiment (5) coincides with the data published in particular in work [5]. For tap water in the temperature range 18-22°C the surface tension is given approximately by [5] $\sigma \approx (0.065 \div 0.068) N/m$ which coincides with the result obtained in the expression (5).

The results obtained were used by one of the authors in modelling problems [6,7].

Conclusions

Based on the results obtained in the experiment, we can conclude that The deviation of the surface tension coefficient values $\sigma = 0.066 N/m$ from those for clean water $\sigma = 0.0728 N/m$ for water pipe water is close to those values given in reference books [5,8]. Determining the composition of impurities when finding the surface tension coefficient makes it possible to roughly estimate the purity (of type salt of calcium, magnesium, chlorine organic substances, sometimes detergent substances in small quantities) in water and the contribution of impurities that pollute it. It can be seen from the formula (4) that increasing the number of drop measurements when determining liquid tension, relative non-increase the density and volume, and the diameter of the capillaries makes it possible to reduce the error. Estimating the surface tension coefficient makes it possible to estimate the liquid tension of substances, especially in practice.

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